

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE INTENTION AND DECISION OF CHINESE HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS TO STUDY AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN MALAYSIA

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Abstract:

The internationalization of higher education has provided more opportunities for China students. In view of the problems of studying abroad and cross-border of higher education, a large number of studies have been found in Malaysia. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to find out the main factors that influence the choice of Chinese high school students to study in Malaysia. Theory of planned behaviour (TPB) has been applied in this study considering the theory essentially studied consumer behaviour especially in the field of marketing. The target population of this study is all the third-year high school students, who are in the urban area of four third-tier cities in Jiangxi province of China and the unit of analysis is every third-year high school student, who is in the urban area of four third-tier cities in Jiangxi province of China. In this study, the unlimited probability sampling design or simple random sampling is utilized. It was found in this study that academic expectation is not significant in influencing China's students' intention to study in Malaysia and China's student intention to study in Malaysia does not mediate between academic expectation and decision to study in Malaysian higher education institution. With the vast population of China with different demographic settings due to cultural and background differences, this study may not have conclusively covered all spectrum for this study. However, this can be done by having a larger coverage of China target population, entrepreneur or marketers have to hire a highly qualified academic staffs to convey appropriate and high-quality knowledge to the students. The brand equity of foreign students was one of the significant factors that impact their enrolment in of higher education institution. Notably,

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this study improves the current written literature on influential factors towards intention of student enrolment in of higher education institution. However, future researchers are advisable to ensure target respondents of questionnaire survey are distributed fairly based on the region and to produce a result with higher generalizability and representative for all foreign students.

Keywords: intention and decision, Chinese high school students, higher education institutions in Malaysia

1. Introduction

Since the twenty-first Century, the globalization of education has been greatly developed through the flow of international students. The number of overseas students in the world has increased and increased significantly year by year. The proportion of Asian students is increasing, while the proportion of students from Europe is significantly less. Asian students mainly come from East Asia, especially China, while European students mainly come from the European Union. Middle income countries have the largest number of overseas studying abroad (Fu, 2016).

The increase in foreign enrolment has been driven by a variety of domestic and external factors. The skills' needs for knowledge-based and innovation-driven economies have spurred demand for tertiary education worldwide; however, local education capacities have not evolved rapid enough to meet growing domestic demand (UNESCO, 2013).

The policy of studying abroad in China has gone through the process of continuous change and development. It has gradually formed a set of comprehensive system of management and service for studying abroad, which is preferred for individual development. The three channels include national funded studying abroad, public funded studying abroad and individual funded studying abroad, which are complementary and mutually beneficial. By the end of 2016, China has established educational cooperation and exchange relations with 188 countries and regions, cooperated with 46 important international organizations and signed mutual recognition agreements with 47 countries and regions (China Education Daily, 2018).

The expansion of Malaysia's higher education system is closely related to the steady development of Malaysia's economy and the government's encouragement to the development of private higher education in Malaysia. It has long been working with the universities of Britain, Australia and the United States to carry out various courses, and English is being used as a teaching language as the main language. The strengthening of Malaysia's economic has laid a solid economic foundation for the government to invest heavily in education. With economic growth, the government's investment in education has been steadily increasing. Thus, the government of Malaysia has adopted more open education policy and carried out a comprehensive and in-depth reform of higher education. The implementation of these measures has promoted the rapid expansion of

the scale of higher education in Malaysia, improved the overall quality and level of higher education, and promoted the cooperation and communication between Malaysia universities and foreign universities. To a certain extent, the pull and competitiveness of Malaysia institutions of higher learning in the global international student education market have been enhanced directly or indirectly, laying a solid foundation for attracting a large number of neighboring and distant state students and promoting the development of foreign students' Education in Malaysia. In 2013-2017, the number of Chinese students and foreign students enrolled by HEIs in Malaysia are shown in Table 1. Over the past five years, the number of foreign students enrolled by higher education institution in Malaysia has been increasing year by year. At the same time, the number of Chinese students is the main foreign students in Malaysia.

Table 1: The Enrolment of Chinese Students and Foreign Students by HEIs in Malaysia, 2013-2017

Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Enrolment of Chinese students	4,398	7,055	10,775	11,718	14,854
Enrolment of Foreign students	52,598	74,996	120,398	130,277	133,860
Proportion of Chinese students and foreign students	8.36%	9.41%	8.95%	8.99%	11.97%

Source: Ministry of Higher Education of Malaysia (2018).

Besides, 56% of Chinese students are pursuing their studies at universities in Canada (Wang & Miao, 2017). The internationalization of higher education has provided more opportunities for China students. Thus, in view of the problems of studying abroad and cross-border of higher education, a large number of studies have been found in Malaysia, mainly to understand students' perception to study in Malaysia and students from Malaysia to study in a foreign country. However, there are not many studies mainly to understand the determinants of Chinese students to choose Malaysia for tertiary education.

According to Andrade (2006), foreign students have contributed to intercultural learning and increase the understanding of diversity and to understand the global issues of a local country. Nevertheless, Malaysian students indirectly be benefited through more exposure on foreigner's culture as well as build understanding between each other (Schneider, 2000 as cited in Andrade, 2006). Therefore, the main objective of this study is to find out the main factors that influence the choice of Chinese high school students to study in Malaysia.

2. Literature Review

There are four basic characteristics in cross-border higher education: the first is the economic value orientation, the second is the tendency of [marketization](#), the third is the fuzzy boundary, and the fourth is the pattern innovation (Gu, 2008). There are four main forms of cross-border higher education: the flow of international students, the flow of

projects, the flow of institutions and the hub of education, among which the flow of international students is one of the most important forms of cross-border higher education (Zhang, 2009). Cross-border education is divided into four types: cross border flow, cross-border movement of projects, cross-border flow of educational institutions and cross-border flow of services. This classification method has also been recognized by OECD (Knight, 2011). The theory of cultural capital is from the angle of social stratification and flow, and thinks that cross-border education is an important way for the elite to maintain the superiority of the class by accepting high quality higher education (Yue, 2017).

Theories related to the students' decision to study abroad are a combination of college choice theories for domestic students and migration theories. Considering the college choice of domestic students, sociological models come first. These models focus on how students' social and psychological structures influence the choice of higher education institutions (Hossler, Schmit, & Vesper, 1999; McDonough, 1997; Plank, & Jordan, 2001). These models investigate the effect of socioeconomic status, family conditions, school environment, individual characteristics, and school adjustment on college choice (Hossler et al., 1999; Paulsen, 1990). However, students are not just affected by surrounding factors (Kotler & Fox, 1985). In this way, the college choice process follows certain steps, such as need arousal, information search, evolution of alternatives, decision implementation, and post-enrollment evaluation (Kotler & Fox, 1985). These two different perspectives on college choice are gathered together in combined models assuming that the choice of the college is an incremental process rather than a single decision (Hossler et al., 1999). This process consists of three stages: predisposition, search, and choice. The prestige of the foreign colleges, career opportunities after graduation, and opportunities offered by the host country to international students are among the pulling factors, while different obstacles, such as low quality of education and political or economic turmoil in the country are examples of the push factors (Altbach, 2004; Mazzarol & Soutar 2002; McMahan, 1992). Mazzaroul and Soutar (2002) examined the process of college choice in three stages: deciding to study internationally or nationally, selection of the host country, and selection of the institution.

3. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Theory of planned behaviour (TPB) has been applied in various studies which essentially studied consumer behaviour especially in the field of marketing (Mishra, 2014). Besides, TPB advocates that consumer behaviour is predominantly predicted by intention (Ajzen, 1991; Armitage & Conner, 2001 as cited in Ooi, 2009). Generally, TPB is known as a cognitive model of human behavior which concentrates in predicting and understanding the clearly defined behaviors (Hsu, 2012). TPB model inherently comprises of attitude toward the behavior, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975 as cited in Astuti & Martdianty, 2012).

The first antecedent of intention is attitude toward the behavior. It is related to the extent of an individual has a positive or negative evaluation of the behavior (Hsu, 2012). Next, the second antecedent of intention is subjective norm. It is a social element which referring to perceived social pressures whether to perform or not to perform the behavior (Astuti & Martdianty, 2012). Whereas for normative belief are focused with the likelihood that significant referent individuals or groups accept or reject of performing a given behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). While the last antecedent is the degree of perceived behavioral control which refers to the perception regarding whether the performances of the behavior is easy or difficult (Hsu, 2012). According to Dumitrescu, Wagle, Dogaru and Manolescu (2011) revealed that intention is the strongest determinant of behavior. In addition, an intention is often influenced by attitude, subjective norm and perceive behavioral control toward the behavior (Dumitrescu et al., 2011). According to Downs and Hausenblas (2005), stronger intention behavior association should occur in shorter time periods instead of longer time periods because it will lead to inconsistency of measurement.

The rational of behavior theory assumes that the occurrence of behavior can be controlled by the will of the individual. However, in the actual situation, the individual's control of the will is often disturbed by many other factors, which greatly reduces the explanatory power of the individual behavior in the theory of rational behavior. According to [Ajzen & Fishbein](#) (1980) and [Fishbein & Ajzen](#) (1975), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is developed by the combination of Theory of Multi-attribute Attitude and Theory of Reasoned Action.

Ajzen (1980) extended the theory of rational behavior and put forward the theory of planned behavior. In addition to the attitude and subjective criteria, behavioral intention will be influenced by the control of perceived behavior. The theory mainly includes five factors, such as behavior attitude, subjective criterion, perception behavior control, behavior intention and behavior, and systematically expounds the interaction and mutual influence of these elements. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), human activity is guided by three sorts of contemplations:

- 1) Behavioral Beliefs (convictions about the reasonable outcomes of the behavior)
- 2) Normative Beliefs (convictions about the normative desires for others).
- 3) Control Beliefs (convictions about the presence of variables that may encourage or obstruct execution of the behavior).

Behavioral beliefs create a great or horrible disposition toward the behavior. Normative beliefs result in see social weight or subjective standard, and control beliefs offer ascent to apparent conduct control. In blend, attitude towards the behavior, subjective norm, and impression of social control prompt the development of a behavior expectation. When in doubt, the more positive state of attitude and subjective norm, the more prominent the apparent control and the more grounded should the people intention to play out the behavior being referred to. Since the theory of planned behavior has been put forward, numerous research have been widely used in various fields and levels, such as sports leisure behavior, health medical behavior, learning behavior, consumption

behavior and so on, which have fully proved that the theory can well explain and predict the individual's behavior intention and behavior results (Wang, 2014).

3.1 Relevance of TPB to this study

This study combines perceive behavioral control and attitude toward behavior and refer this combination as the student belief. Beliefs and the corresponding attitudes expected to affect intentions that lead to the actual behavior (Schnusenberg et al., 2012). On top of that, subjective norm is referred as social influence. In this study, social influence can be described as influence by parents, friend and teacher in affecting the perception of foreign students to enroll in Malaysia's higher education institution. On the other hand, based on the past studies, it has been highlighted that student enrolment decision making is constructed by a combination of pull-push factors (Maringe & Carter, 2007 as cited in Padlee et al., 2010). The push factors refer to the condition that operates in the country and initiate students' decision to undertake international study (Phang, 2013). While pull factors is associated to the attraction or benefit of study destination will gain by the foreign student when study in host countries (Wilkins & Huisman, 2011). Another study indicates that TPB can be applied to explain about the push and pull factors are able to influence individual's career decision (Baruch et.al as cited in Cieri, Sheehan, Costa, Fenwick & Cooper, 2007). In addition, this theory predicts that the actual response of the students (to stay or to return to their homeland) will be positively related to their tendency to do so and it will be affected by their attitude (Baruch, Budhwar & Khatri, 2007). Moreover, in this study social influence is considered as one of the push factors that affects the foreign students' enrolment whereas brand equity has high impact that forms main attraction for foreign students' enrolment in higher education institution.

3.2 Empirical Reviews of China's Factors

Through descriptive statistics and t-test, it was found that the driving factors in China have a significant impact on students' intention to go abroad for higher education, such as the quality of Chinese universities, the pressure of college entrance examination, admission opportunities, curriculum design, teachers' level and relatively backward teaching and research facilities (Sun, 2017). Kuang & Qi (2016) conducted a thrust analysis on Chinese students studying in Australia and believed that China's relaxed environment for studying abroad, the long-standing imbalance between supply and demand of higher education in China and the substantial increase in the per capita payable income of China constitute a strong push for students' self-funded studying abroad. In addition, the concept of family investment in children's higher education has changed, and the mature and convenient service industry for studying abroad has also played a positive role in promoting people's decision-making on studying abroad.

Sun (2017), Zhao (2016) and Kuang & Qi (2016) proposed that the single college entrance examination selection system, the severe employment situation and the disappointment of Chinese education are the reasons for students and parents to start looking for easy and high-quality overseas higher education resources and choose to

study abroad. Gao (2014) made a detailed investigation by means of questionnaires and interviews on many factors in the phenomenon of primary and secondary school students studying abroad in Dalian city, Liaoning province. The survey found that different factors of China's social aspects (China's relaxed policy of studying abroad, China's pressure of entering higher education and employment, the increasing frequency of international exchanges), China's education aspects (differences in educational methods, limitations of the system of entering schools, the simplicity of curriculum, rigidity of the educational system and obsolescence of educational concepts) and China's family aspects (growth of private wealth, from Driven by the psychology of the masses) together caused more and more primary and secondary school students in Dalian city to choose to study abroad. Philip (2005) and other researchers found that the overly demanding or biased enrollment policy made many talented students unable to enter the ideal National University, and promoted the students to choose to go abroad to receive higher education.

The number of college graduates in China in 2017 reached 7.95 million, an increase of 160,000 over last year. Since 2011, the number of graduates has been increasing year by year with a year-on-year growth rate of 2% to 5%, and the cumulative number of graduates has reached 50.75 million in the past seven years (China Industrial Development Research Network, 2017).

Many studies have found that in the face of increasing employment pressure in China, many Chinese parents and college students believe that the higher value of overseas degree and stronger employment competitiveness in China's employment market will prompt them to choose to study abroad (Zhan, 2017; Gao, 2014; Liu et al., 2012; Liu & Fang, 2011; Li and Mark Bray, 2007). Many studies have proved that the current situation of higher education (HE) in China has promoted Chinese students to study abroad. Axel & Panu (2005), Lu et al. (2014), Pang (2001), Lu et al. (2014) and other researchers proposed that the relatively low education quality of higher education substitutions in China and the lack experienced lecturers are the main reasons the students choose to study abroad. Altbach (1998), Lu et al. (2014) and other researchers suggested that the relatively backward curriculum in China given rise for students to choose to study abroad. The lack of educational facilities and scientific research equipment is also a factor leading to students studying abroad (Pang, 2001; Nankai University research group, 2013). Moreover, from the literature review, the following hypotheses can be constructed.

H1: Social Influence (SI) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)

H2: Academic Expectation (AE) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)

H3: Foreign Economic Condition (FC) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)

H4: Quality of Foreign Education (QE) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)

H5: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) has a relationship with CM

H6: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of Social Influence (SI) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)

H7: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of Academic Expectation (AE) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)

H8: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of Foreign Economic Condition (FC) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)

H9: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of Quality of Foreign Education (QE) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)

3. Research Methodology

According to the theory of TRA and TPB application in the field of education, the intention refers to the tendency of Chinese high school students to make a decision and choose to study in Malaysia. Their perceptions and attitudes towards the influence of Chinese factors, Malaysian factors and their conditions and motivations, will affect their intention and choice to study in Malaysia. The target population of this study is all the third-year high school students, who are in the urban area of four third-tier cities (Ganzhou, Jiujiang, Shangrao and Yichun) in Jiangxi province of China and the unit of analysis is every third-year high school student, who is in the urban area of four third-tier cities (Ganzhou, Jiujiang, Shangrao and Yichun) in Jiangxi province of China. In this study, the unlimited probability sampling design or simple random sampling is utilized.

4. Analysis and Findings

The demographic analysis of 428 completed questionnaires this study found that there are more males than females with 54.9% male and 45.1% female. This result of statistics is supported by Liu (2015) and sun (2017), that is, there are more males than females among Chinese overseas students. As can be seen from the descriptive data, among the high school students who are willing to study abroad, the majority of their fathers have received higher education, accounting for 58.4%. As can be seen from the above data, among the high school students who are willing to study abroad, the majority of their mothers have received higher education, accounting for 50.9%. It can be concluded that, for this study, majority parents are intellectuals, professionals and technical personnel. Most of the students are from a middle-income family with parents earning RMB110,000 to RMB150,000 and only the smallest proportion of family household of 26 (6.1%) for households with an annual income of RMB50,000 below. Thus, through the demographic

analysis, it can be concluded that the father's occupation and mother's occupation are public servants, intellectuals and professional and technical personnel and employers, and the annual income of the family is relatively higher.

In this study, the results of questionnaire reliability analysis are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of Reliability Analysis of Questionnaire Scale

Construct	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Social Influence (SI)	5	0.908
Academic Expectation (AE)	5	0.892
Foreign Economic Condition (FC)	5	0.806
Quality of Foreign Education (QE)	5	0.912
Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)	5	0.873
Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)	5	0.853

As can be seen from the above Table 2, Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of all variables in this study are all greater than 0.8, indicating that they all have strong reliability.

The Chi-Square value of Bartlett's Test in Table 3 shows Sphericity is 2518.996, and the df is 45. The results show that significance P value is $0.000 < 0.001$, reaching a very significant level. This indicates that the scale factors are suitable for factor analysis.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test of Push of China's Factors (PC)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.913
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2518.996
	df	45
	Sig.	.000

The factor loading coefficient after rotation is greater than 0.5. Therefore, the analysis results show that the structural validity of the PC scale is good as shown in Table 4.

4.1 Result of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Through exploratory factor analysis (EFA) of the scales of six variables, it can be seen that the KMO value of each variable scale is greater than 0.7, and the P value of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is significant. The common factor structure of each variable scale is clear, and the cumulative variance interpretation rate is high, so the questionnaire has a good structural validity. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Variable	KMO	Sig.	Factors	Variance	Items
Social Influence (SI)	0.913	.000	2	69.227%	10
Academic Expectation (AE)	0.896	.000	2	66.155%	10
Foreign Economic Condition (FC)	0.903	.000	2	67.224%	10
Quality of Foreign Education (QE)	0.919	.000	2	71.828%	10
Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)	0.827	.000	1	72.859%	4

Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)	0.819	.000	1	69.761%	4
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4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Overall Structural Model

This study has carried out confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) on the measurement models of six variables, and the analysis results show that the fit indexes of the models all reach ideal values, indicating that the fitting degree of each measurement model and data is good. The standardized load coefficient of each item is basically greater than 0.6. Each measurement model has good composite reliability and convergent validity, so the intrinsic quality of this questionnaire scale is very good. The fitting indices of modified structural equation model are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Fitting index list of Modified Structural Equation Model

Fitness Index	Critical Value	Test Data	Fitting Judgment
X2		1184.756	
df		1061	
X2/df	1-3	1.117	Yes
SRMR	<0.05	0.046	Yes
GFI	> 0.9	0.900	Yes
AGFI	> 0.9	0.889	Close to 0.9
NFI	> 0.9	0.907	Yes
IFI	> 0.9	0.989	Yes
TLI	> 0.9	0.989	Yes
CFI	> 0.9	0.989	Yes
RMSEA	<0.08	0.017	Yes

Table 5 shows that the fitting indices $GFI=0.900 \geq 0.9$, $AGFI=0.889$ close to 0.90, $NFI=0.907 > 0.90$, $CFI=0.989$, $RMSAE=0.017 < 0.05$, $SRMR=0.046 < 0.05$ in the modified structural equation model, all of which are ideal values, indicating that the modified structural equation model is acceptable. The corresponding path parameters are shown in Table 6, which provides a basis for later hypothesis testing.

Table 6: The Path Parameter List of Modified Structural Equation Model

Construct Path		S.E.	C.R. (T-value)	P	Standardized Estimate (Beta)	
SI	----- >	IM	0.057	6.550	***	0.363
AE	----- >	IM	0.064	1.073	0.283	0.057
FC	----- >	IM	0.084	5.584	***	0.313
QE	----- >	IM	0.078	7.682	***	0.443
IM	----- >	CM	0.060	10.538	***	0.577

Table 7 shows that the Chinese Students' Social Influence (SI), Foreign Economic Condition (FC), Quality of Education (QE) has significant impact on intention to study in

Malaysia Higher Education Institution, and the Intention to study in Malaysia (IM) have a significant impact on the Chinese Students' decision to Study in Malaysia (CM). Further, the bootstrapping is adapted to test whether the mediation effect was significant. The method adopted Bootstrap ML with 2000 repeated sampling to test the mediation effect results. Its 95% confidence interval contains 0, indicating no mediation, and if 0 is not included, indicating mediation, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: The List of Bootstrap Mediation Effect

Mediation Path	Standardized Estimate	S.E.	Percentile method (95%)		
			Lower Bounds	Upper Bounds	P
SI--IM--CM	$0.363 \times 0.577 = 0.209$	0.034	0.144	0.277	0.001
AE--IM--CM	$0.057 \times 0.577 = 0.033$	0.034	-0.031	0.105	0.311
FC--IM--CM	$0.313 \times 0.577 = 0.180$	0.033	0.115	0.246	0.001
QE--IM--CM	$0.443 \times 0.577 = 0.255$	0.033	0.191	0.319	0.001

Table 8 shows the four mediation paths and indicates whether the mediation effect exists, which provides a basis for later hypotheses testing.

4.3 Hypotheses Testing

The modified structural equation model is used to test the relationships between the constructs based on the proposed hypotheses. Critical t-values for a two-tailed test are 1.96 (significance level = 5 percent), 2.58 (significance level = 1 percent) and 3.24 (significance level = 0.1 percent). For this study, 5 percent significance level (t-value 1.96) was used as a statistical decision criterion. The result of each hypothesis will be tested and discussed below, total nine (9) hypotheses.

Table 8: The Result of Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Conclusion
H1: Social Influence (SI) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)	Supported
H2: Academic Expectation (AE) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)	Not Supported
H3: Foreign Economic Condition (FC) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)	Supported
H4: Quality of Foreign Education (QE) has a relationship with Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM)	Supported
H5: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) has a relationship with CM	Supported
H6: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of Social Influence (SI) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)	Supported
H7: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of Academic Expectation (AE) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)	Not Supported
H8: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating	Supported

role in the influence of Foreign Economic Condition (FC) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)	
H9: Chinese Students' Intention to Study in Malaysia (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of Quality of Foreign Education (QE) on Chinese Students' Decision to Study in Malaysia (CM)	Supported

5. Conclusion and Managerial Implications

Based on the result, student belief has significant relationship with foreign students' enrolment. As the students are playing their role as customers, it is very important for marketers to refer these studies to construct and ensure the facilities of higher education institution are well-equipped. Furthermore, quality of teaching is a main concern that foreign students to enroll in a of higher education institution. Consequently, entrepreneur or marketers have to hire a highly qualified academic staffs to convey appropriate and high-quality knowledge to the students. The brand equity of foreign students was one of the significant factors that impact their enrolment in of higher education institution. This is due to brand equity is known as the value of the brand in the marketplace which means high brand equity has greater value in the marketplace (Pullig, 2008). Besides, students are more likely to choose the good reputation and higher service quality of higher education institution. Marketers should focus on emphasize the brand of the of higher education institution in order to build a high reputation and positive experiences in the customers' mind. However, it was found in this study that academic expectation has less significant relationship with the foreign students' intention to study in Malaysia. Thus, entrepreneurs who want to establish a of higher education institution have to understand further the reasons for the result of this findings. Marketers can emphasize the facilities of the of higher education institution availability, atmosphere of the HEI and etc. which influence the student belief.

5.1 Theoretical Implications

This research has also contributed to the theoretical implications. Notably, this study improves the current written literature on influential factors towards intention of student enrolment in of higher education institution. The factors being examined are social influence, academic expectation, Country's economic condition and quality of education. According to Shaw (2005) stated that previous studies have offer some examples, recommendations and considerations for institutions savor in structuring and carrying out their own research studies on the educational benefits of diversity. Therefore, it can help researchers to have a clear insight and greater understanding of foreign students' enrolment of higher education institution in Malaysia in future by referring this research study. Next, the findings of this study provide reference for students, academician or researchers who plan to study and research in this field as there is less established research done towards foreign students' enrolment in higher education institution in Malaysia. Last but not least, Universities build a recognizable brand by creating a memorable logo. It should represent that the universities have positive image and it

should be easy for people to make a connection between the brand and the education that attempts to be offered. Besides, it can be used as a guideline for future students to study in Malaysian higher education institution.

5.2 Limitation of the Study

With the vast population of China with different demographic settings due to cultural and background differences, this study may not have conclusively covered all spectrum for this study. However, this can be done by having a larger coverage of China target population. Thus, future researchers are advisable to ensure target respondents of questionnaire survey are distributed fairly based on the region and to produce a result with higher generalizability and representative for all foreign students. Although the questionnaire for this study has been enhanced and corrected after the conduct of pilot study, but there are chances that some respondent might answer the questionnaire without proper consideration because of time constraints. Some of respondents might also giving imprecise respond during the survey as they think and believe that some of the information acquired maybe disrupts their privacy or language barrier among the respondent. These circumstances will influence the researchers from receiving actual and accurate information related to this research.

5.3 Recommendation of Future Research

There are some ways to overcome the limitation mentioned previously. Nevertheless, there are some recommendations to overcome the problem of accuracy and trustable of the data obtain through the questionnaire that leads by the inappropriate answer provided by the respondents due to their language barrier or other factors. Firstly, before distribute the questionnaire to the respondents, the researcher have to give a precise description about the purpose of conducting this questionnaire to let the respondent to felt this questionnaire is safe and the privacy is protected when they are answering the questionnaire. Moreover, the researchers can assist the respondents to answer the questionnaire if they meet any problem when the times, they submit their questionnaire back to the researcher. In a conclusion, this study had achieved the research objective in determining the determinants of foreign student enrolment in Malaysia HEI. Scale measurement with internal scale and inferential analysis has conducted to examine the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. Last but not least, this finding indicates that the three independent variables have a significant relationship towards foreign student enrolment.

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